

New triterpenoids from *Lantana camara* : Isomerisation of the angeloyl moiety of lantadene A during catalytic hydrogenation

S. B. Mahato^{a*}, S. Sharma^b, B. Pramanik^c and O. P. Sharma^b

^aIndian Institute of Chemical Biology, 4 Raja S. C. Mullick Road, Jadavpur, Calcutta-700 032, India

^bIndian Veterinary Research Institute, Regional Station, Palampur-176 061, India

^cSchering Plough Research Institute, 2015 Galloping Hill Road, Kenilworth, New Jersey 07033-0539, U.S.A.

Manuscript received 12 October 1999

Two new triterpenes, 22 β -tigloyloxylantanoic acid (5) and 22 β -dimethylacryloyloxylantanoic acid (6) have been isolated along with 22 β -angeloyloxylantanoic acid (4) and 24-hydroxy-3-oxoolean-12-en-28-oic acid (7) from the leaves of the Common Pink variety of *Lantana camara* var. *aculeata* and their structures elucidated by spectroscopic methods. ¹³C NMR spectral data assignments of lantadenes A, B and C isolated from the red variety of the plant and isomerization of the angeloyl moiety of lantadene A to tigloyl moiety to yield a new product 22 β -tigloyloxy-3-oxoolean-12-en-28-oic acid (10) during catalytic hydrogenation are also reported.

Lantana camara Linn. (Verbenaceae) is a straggling plant now found over a wide area of the tropical and subtropical regions of the world^{1,2}. The plant occurs in different taxa and a detailed botanical survey in Australia led to the recognition of some thirty taxa, of which nine have assumed pest proportions³. The plant is known to be toxic to grazing animals, which on ingestion of the leaves, develop hepatotoxicity and photosensitization⁴. Extensive phytochemical investigation on the plant led to the isolation of a number of triterpenoids, umuhengerin, a partially methylated flavonoid and essential oils⁴. These are nonpolar constituents. The polar compounds isolated from the plant are verbascoside⁵, possessing antimicrobial, immunosuppressive and antitumor activities⁶⁻⁸, and flavonoid and phenylpropanoid glycosides⁹. The allelochemicals from the plant associated with insecticidal, pesticidal and weedcidal activities have been suggested to be polar¹⁰. The plant has also the reputation of being used in traditional medicine¹¹. The triterpenoids of *L. camara* significantly vary between taxa. For example, the taxon, Common Pink is nontoxic to livestock and does not contain lantadene A or lantadene B which are believed to be responsible for toxic effects of the plant. Instead this taxon contains triterpenoids having an oxide bridge from C-25 to C-3 and a hemiketal system at C-3. This paper reports isolation and structure elucidation of two new triterpenoids from the Common Pink taxon, ¹³C NMR spectral data assignments of some triterpenes from the plant and isomerization of the angeloyl moiety of lantadene A during catalytic hydrogenation.

Results and Discussion

Lantana leaves of the Common Pink taxon were air-dried and powdered. The acetone-soluble fraction of the methanolic extract of the powdered leaves on chromatographic purification on silica gel column yielded a residue, designated C-11. This was subjected to HPLC analysis which revealed four major peaks (Fig. 1). Preparative HPLC separation of C-11 using a Supelcosil LC-18-DB column and a gradient-mobile phase of water/acetonitrile containing 0.03% trifluoroacetic acid furnished compounds A, B, C and D. FAB-MS of C-11 in 3-NBA-DMSO matrix and MS/MS of the resulting *m/z* 1039.70 and 1137.7 peaks disclosed that C-11 consisted of compounds of molecular weights 470 and 568. LC-MS of peaks A, B, C and D (Fig. 1) demonstrated that C-11 consisted of compounds A, B, C and D, of which A is the major component, A, B and D are isomers with molecular weight 568 and component C is a different compound with a molecular weight of 470. Dimeric ions were observed in both ESI-LC/MS and FAB spectra. The compounds A, B, C and D were separated by preparative HPLC as mentioned above. The four compounds thus obtained were subjected to ¹H and ¹³C NMR analysis. For comparison of the ¹³C data, the known triterpenes, lantadenes A (1), B (2) and C (3) were isolated from the leaves of the widespread *L. camara* red taxon. Assignment of the ¹³C NMR δ -values of 1, 2 and 3 (Table 1) were made with the help of DEPT (distortionless enhancement by polarization transfer) studies, known chemical shift rules^{12,13} and by comparison with those of appropriate pentacyclic triterpenoids¹⁴. The ¹³C NMR data of compounds A (4), B

† Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

Fig. 1. HPLC of C-11 on a column of Supelcosil LC-18-DB (3.3 cm × 4.6 mm i.d., 3 mm particle size); mobile phase gradient water/acetonitrile 0.03% TFA.

(5), C (6) and D (7) isolated from Common Pink taxon were assigned with the help of DEPT studies as well as by comparison with the ^{13}C values of lantadenes A (1), B (2) and C (3) and recently isolated¹⁵ camarilic acid (8) and camaracinic acid (9) from the aerial parts of *L. camara* (flower colour not mentioned). Thus the compounds 4, 5, 6 and 7 were characterised as 22β-angeloyloxylantanoic acid, 22β-tigloyloxylantanoic acid, 22β-dimethylacryloyloxy-lantanoic acid and 24-hydroxy-3-oxoolean-12-en-28-oic acid, respectively. While a mixture of the 22β-angeloyloxy and 22β-dimethylacryloyloxy derivatives of lantanoic acid has previously been isolated from the plant³, the triterpenes 5 and 6 are new, and triterpene 7 is reported for the first time from the Common Pink variety of the plant.

Isomerisation of lantadene A : Lantadene A (1) dissolved in a mixture of dried ethanol and ethyl acetate was hydrogenated over Pd-C (10%) under pressure (20 psi) for 5.5 h at room temperature (14°). The hydrogenated product obtained after usual workup was purified by column chromatography over silica gel to yield two components. The slightly faster moving component was identified as lantadene C (3). The other component designated as lantadene X (10) appeared to be an unknown compound from its NMR spec-

tral characteristics. Its UV and IR spectra were similar to those of lantadene A (1). The mass spectrum showed the molecular ion peak at m/z 552 which is the same as that of 1. However, the ^1H NMR (see Experimental) and ^{13}C NMR (Table 1) data of 1 and 10 disclosed that these are similar for the ring systems but differ in the values of the acyl moieties. This difference is rationalized by assuming isomerization of the angeloyl group (*cis*-form) to the tigloyl group (*trans*-form). The double bond migration and formation of *trans*-isomers are known to occur extensively during catalytic hydrogenation of unsaturated acids, especially if the reaction is stopped before complete reduction¹⁶. The discernible ^1H NMR data of product 10 and the ^{13}C values were found to be compatible with the structure 22β-tigloyloxy-3-oxoolean-12-en-28-oic acid and could be assigned by comparison with those of compounds with similar skeleta.

It is noteworthy that triterpenes 4, 5 and 6 possess an

Table 1. ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts δ_{C} (± 0.1) of compounds 1-7 and 10

Carbon no.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	10
1	39.1	39.2	39.2	34.7	34.6	34.8	39.0	39.2
2	34.1	34.1	34.1	28.0	27.9	27.8	34.2	34.1
3	217.5	217.5	217.5	100.3	100.2	100.3	217.5	217.5
4	47.4	47.4	47.4	38.5	38.5	38.8	47.3	47.5
5	55.3	55.3	55.4	50.8	50.7	50.8	55.4	55.4
6	19.5	19.8	19.6	19.5	19.5	19.6	18.5	19.6
7	32.2	32.2	32.3	31.0	30.9	31.1	32.7	32.3
8	39.3	39.3	39.3	40.8	40.7	40.6	39.9	39.3
9	46.9	46.9	46.9	42.0	42.1	41.9	47.8	46.9
10	36.8	36.8	36.8	35.1	35.1	34.9	36.6	36.8
11	23.5	23.6	23.6	23.9	23.8	23.6	23.7	23.6
12	122.5	122.5	122.5	122.7	122.6	126.0	122.2	122.6
13	143.1	143.1	143.0	143.3	143.2	137.4	143.7	143.2
14	42.0	42.1	42.1	42.0	42.1	42.2	41.9	42.1
15	27.6	27.6	27.6	27.9	27.8	28.0	27.7	27.6
16	24.2	24.1	24.3	24.2	24.1	24.6	23.6	24.0
17	50.6	50.6	50.6	50.8	50.7	51.0	46.8	50.7
18	38.5	38.7	38.6	39.0	38.6	39.1	41.5	38.5
19	46.0	46.0	46.0	46.0	46.1	49.2	45.9	46.0
20	30.0	30.0	30.0	30.1	30.1	38.5	30.7	30.0
21	36.8	36.8	37.0	37.0	36.9	34.9	33.8	36.8
22	75.9	75.2	75.6	75.8	76.1	75.7	32.5	76.2
23	26.4	26.5	26.5	27.0	27.1	27.1	26.5	26.5
24	21.4	21.4	21.5	17.1	17.2	17.0	64.6	21.5
25	16.9	16.9	16.8	67.7	67.8	67.7	15.8	17.0
26	20.5	21.1	21.5	21.0	21.1	21.0	16.8	21.5
27	26.1	26.3	26.2	26.1	26.2	26.0	26.1	26.2
28	179.6	178.4	177.3	179.6	178.1	178.3	179.8	178.3
29	33.6	33.7	33.6	33.7	33.8	17.4	33.2	33.7
30	25.8	25.8	25.7	25.6	25.7	21.3	23.7	25.8
1'	166.3	165.3	175.2	166.5	166.6	165.4		166.6
2'	127.7	116.0	41.4	127.7	128.6	116.1		128.5
3'	138.8	157.0	38.0	138.3	137.8	157.1		137.7
4'	15.1	15.1	15.1	15.0	12.0	15.1		11.9
5'	15.6	20.4	16.5	15.8	14.5	20.4		14.4

oxide bridge from C 25 to C 3 with an acetal system at C 3. This type of acids such as lantanolic acid and lantic acid are already known constituents of the Common Pink variety of Indian *L. camara*^{17,18}. Lantabetulic acid, another triterpene of this type, has been isolated from Australian Common Pink taxon³. As already mentioned, two triterpenes of this type have been reported from Pakistan¹⁵. Although the Pakistani authors have not mentioned the flower colour of the

L. camara they investigated, it is likely that it was Common Pink variety. It may be noted that lantanolic acid is the first example of a triterpene hydroxylated at C 25, and compounds of this type have only been so far known to occur in *L. camara*. Although triterpene 7 has been isolated from *L. camara*,³ it appears that this is the first report of occurrence of this acid in the Common Pink variety.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on 300 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Reverse-phase high pressure liquid chromatography-electrospray ionisation mass spectrometry (RP-LC-ESI MS) was carried out on a Shimadzu HPLC system equipped with two LC-10-AD pumps (Japan). Well-resolved chromatographic peaks were obtained on a Supelcosil LC-18-DB column (4.6 mm i.d. \times 3.3 cm, 3 μm particle size) using a 0.03% trifluoroacetic acid-water-acetonitrile gradient. A step gradient from 5 to 95% acetonitrile with 1 ml/min flow was used to separate the mixture (5 to 50% ACN in 5 min and 50 to 95% ACN in 5 min). A SCIEX API 100 quadrupole mass spectrometer with a pneumatically assisted electrospray interface (PE – SCIEX, Thornhill, ON, Canada) was used to acquire the mass spectra. The mass spectrometer was operated under low orifice voltage (OR = 30 V) with unit mass resolution across the mass range of interest. Full-scan mass spectra covering mass range of 300–2200 amu were acquired at a step size of 1 amu with a scan time of 2 s.

Isolation of the triterpenoid mixture C-11 : *Lantana camara* var. *aculeata* leaf samples were collected from the vicinity of Panjab University, Chandigarh Campus. Flower colour of the plant was yellow on anthesis but changed pink on maturity. The samples were air-dried, finely ground and extracted with methanol. The methanol extract was processed as usual and chromatographed on neutral alumina and also silica gel eluting with solvents and mixture of solvents with increasing order of polarity. The triterpene mixture designated C-11 was obtained from the benzene-diethyl ether (7 : 3) eluant.

The separation of the constituents of C-11 was achieved by reverse-phase high pressure liquid chromatography as described above. Thus triterpenes A (4), B (5), C (6) and D (7) were obtained in pure condition. *22 β -Angeloyloxylantanolic acid* (4) : Micro-needles (MeOH), m.p. 280–282 $^\circ$; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} +151^\circ$ (*c*, 1.2 in CHCl_3); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 0.83 (3H, s), 0.88 (3H, s), 0.95 (3H, s), 0.99 (3H, s), 1.01 (3H, s), 1.05 (3H, s), 1.75 (3H, s), 1.95 (3H, d, *J* 7 Hz), 4.23 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz), 3.90 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz) (25-H₂); ^{13}C NMR

(Table 1); HRMS m/z $[M+H]^+$ 569.3848; $C_{35}H_{53}O_6$ requires 569.3842. **22 β -Tigloyloxylantanic acid (5)**: Needles (MeOH), m.p. 284–285°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +166^\circ$ (c , 1.1 in $CHCl_3$); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 0.84 (3H, s), 0.86 (3H, s), 0.98 (3H, s), 1.02 (3H, s), 1.05 (3H, s), 1.10 (3H, s), 1.71 (3H, s), 1.75 (3H, s), 4.22 (1H, d, J 10 Hz), 3.90 (1H, d, J 10 Hz) (25- H_2); ^{13}C NMR (Table 1); HRMS m/z $[M+H]^+$ 569.3848; $C_{35}H_{53}O_6$ requires 569.3842. **22 β -Dimethyl-acryloyloxylantic acid (6)**: Flakes (MeOH), m.p. 269–270°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +151^\circ$ (c , 1.16 in $CHCl_3$); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 0.82 (3H, s), 0.85 (3H, s), 0.87 (3H, d, J 7 Hz), 0.89 (3H, d, J 7 Hz), 1.02 (3H, s), 1.05 (3H, s), 1.78 (3H, s), 1.86 (3H, s), 4.21 (1H, d, J 10 Hz), 3.89 (1H, d, J 10 Hz) (25- H_2); ^{13}C NMR (Table 1); HRMS m/z $[M+H]^+$ 569.3848; $C_{35}H_{53}O_6$ requires 569.3842. **24-Hydroxy-3-oxoolean-12-en-28-oic acid (7)**: Needles (MeOH), m.p. 209–211°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +121^\circ$ (c , 1.4 in $CHCl_3$); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 0.80 (3H, s), 0.89 (3H, s), 0.95 (3H, s), 1.14 (3H, s), 1.25 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (Table 1).

22 β -Tigloyloxy-3-oxoolean-12-en-28-oic acid (10; Lantadene X): Lantadene A (**1**; 830 mg) was dissolved in a mixture of dried ethanol (40 ml) and ethyl acetate (160 ml) by warming at 50–60°. The solution was mixed up with Pd-C (400 mg; 10%) and hydrogenated on stirring for 5.5 h under H_2 (20 psi) at room temperature (14°). Worked up in the usual way and the residue consisting of product **10** and lantadene C (**3**) was purified by column chromatography on silica gel followed by crystallization from MeOH to yield product **10** as micro-needles, m.p. 235–237°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +102^\circ$ (c , 1.0 in $CHCl_3$); MS m/z 552 $[M]^+$; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 0.84 (3H, s), 0.89 (3H, s), 0.98 (3H, s), 1.05 (3H, s), 1.06 (3H, s), 1.09 (3H, s), 1.18 (3H, s), 1.71 (3H, s, 5'-H), 1.76 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, 4'-H), 5.02 (1H, t, 22-H), 5.41 (1H, t, 12-H) and 6.77 (1H, q, J 7 Hz, 4'-H); ^{13}C NMR (Table 1).

References

- O. P. Sharma, H. P. S. Makkar and D. K. Dawra, *Toxicon*, 1988, **26**, 975.
- M. A. Pass, *Aust. Vet. J.*, 1986, **63**, 169.
- N. K. Hart, J. A. Lamberton, A. A. Sioumis and H. Soares, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1976, **29**, 655.
- O. P. Sharma and P. D. Sharma, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.* 1989, **48**, 471.
- J. M. Herbert, J. P. Maffrand, K. Taoubi, J. M. Augereau, I. Fouraste and J. Gleye, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1991, **54**, 1595.
- K. Endo and H. Hikino, *Heterocycles*, 1982, **19**, 2033.
- H. Sasaki, H. Nisimura, T. Morota, M. Chim, H. Wei and X. Yu-Lang, *Planta Med.*, 1989, **55**, 458.
- G. Pettit, A. Niumata, T. Takemura, R. Ode, A. Narula, J. Schmidt, G. Cragg and C. Pase, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1990, **53**, 456.
- S. B. Mahato, N. P. Sahu, S. K. Roy and O. P. Sharma, *Tetrahedron*, 1994, **50**, 9439.
- N. R. Acchireddy, M. Singh, L. L. Acchireddy, H. N. Nigg and S. Nagy, *J. Chem. Ecol.*, 1985, **11**, 979.
- J. A. Duke in "Handbook of Medicinal Herbs", CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1985, p. 226.
- J. B. Stothers, "Carbon-13 NMR Spectroscopy", Academic, New York, 1972.
- F. W. Wehrli and T. Wirthlin, "Interpretation of Carbon-13 NMR Spectra", Heyden, London, 1980.
- S. B. Mahato and A. P. Kundu, *Phytochemistry*, 1994, **37**, 1517.
- S. Begum, S. M. Raja, B. S. Siddiqui and S. Siddiqui, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1995, **58**, 1570.
- E. S. West, W. R. Todd, H. S. Mason and J. T. Van Bruggen, "Text Book of Biochemistry", 4th. ed., Macmillan, New York, 1966.
- A. K. Barua, P. Chakrabarti, S. P. Dutta, D. K. Mukherjee and B. C. Das, *Tetrahedron*, 1971, **27**, 1141.
- A. K. Barua, P. Chakrabarti, P. K. Sanyal and B. C. Das, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 100.